

Assessing the potential of heterogeneous mechanical tests for sheet metals through experimentally measured full-fields

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Abstract

Numerical simulation is becoming essential in the mechanical design of sheet metal components, requiring advanced material models, which are composed of many unknown parameters, to accurately describe complex material behaviors. Traditionally, these parameters are identified through multiple quasi-homogeneous tests, each providing specific mechanical data on a particular strain state. The emergence of heterogeneous mechanical tests has revolutionized this process by enabling the capture of a wide range of strain states in a single experiment. This study focuses on the experimental analysis of three heterogeneous mechanical tests, previously studied numerically. Uniaxial tensile tests were conducted on three different specimen designs, using Stereo Digital Image Correlation to capture the mechanical fields on the surface. The repeatability of these tests is checked due to their complex designs. The main objective is to confirm the quality and relevance of the mechanical deformation observed when using real data and evaluate the sensitivity of these tests to different high-strength steels. The results show that heterogeneous mechanical tests, combined with full-field measurement techniques, can provide detailed mechanical behavior data from a single test, reducing the number of tests needed for advanced material characterization.

Keywords: Heterogeneous tests, Experimental analysis, Digital Image Correlation, Material behavior, Sheet metal

1 Introduction

Numerical simulation has become an essential tool for the reliable and efficient mechanical design of new metallic components. Finite element simulations have made it possible to digitalize sheet metal forming operations, reducing the number of failed processes, and shortening the development lead time of new parts. However, for the numerical model to accurately reproduce the most common complex material behaviors present in sheet metal processes, an advanced material model is required. Such a model usually involves many parameters to be identified and therefore requests mechanical data from many quasi-homogeneous tests. Each one of these tests requires a homogeneous mechanical state for the direct derivation of strain and stress [1]. Mechanical tests with heterogeneous fields have been investigated to speed up this task and reduce the experimental effort. Due to their complex configurations or loading conditions, multiple strain and stress states may occur in the specimens, increasing the mechanical behavior information provided by a single test. However, when dealing with heterogeneous tests, full-field measurement techniques and inverse identification methods are mandatory. With the development of full-field measurement techniques such as Digital Image Correlation [2], it is theoretically possible to obtain a heterogeneous strain or displacement field on the surface of the specimen [3]. A large number of material model parameters can therefore be identified using the full-field data from a single heterogeneous test, reducing the number of tests required for the procedure. Since it is not possible to compute the stress and strain components directly from the experimental data, the use of inverse methods [4] is required to solve the identification problem iteratively. This integrated approach, often referred to as Material Testing 2.0 [5], is showcased in recent literature [1, 6, 7].

Numerous studies, mostly numerical ones, have explored the use of heterogeneous mechanical tests along with full-field measurements for inverse identification procedures, as evidenced by the following works [3, 8–16]. These works address the use of different test configurations for improving material models' accuracy. Several attempts have already been made in recent years to propose a test configuration capable of providing sufficient mechanical information for the model calibration procedure on its own [17]. A few works have numerically analyzed in detail the potential of heterogeneous mechanical tests for model calibration based on mechanical indicators [18–20]. From the strain field richness to the model parameters' identifiability, the performance of several mechanical tests was compared, showing the importance of the test designs for the accuracy of the calibration. From these works, it is possible to establish two main approaches for test design that can be summarized under two objectives: the maximization of the strain/stress states present in a test [8, 9, 16, 21–30] and the accuracy of the identified material model parameters [12, 31–36]. On the one hand, the presence of a wider strain/stress state range leads to a richer mechanical test, from which a larger quantity of material behavior information can be extracted. The maximization of the strain state diversity has been made through empirical [12, 16, 21, 22] and optimization approaches [8, 9, 27–30]. On the other hand, the use of the identification error as a criterion for the test design process has been addressed more recently, with the possibility of introducing the meteorological DIC parameters in the optimization process [12, 34, 35]. Most of these works propose numerical methodologies for the

design of new test configurations. However, only some of these obtained geometries have been applied to experiments, especially for thin sheets.

Kim et al. [11] designed a specimen shape to show heterogeneous stress fields under uniaxial loading. Specimen geometries were retrieved from a rolled sheet of 1.2 mm thickness of DP780 steel and analyzed experimentally. The full-field data extracted by stereo digital image correlation was used to identify the hardening and anisotropic material model parameters using VFM. A mechanical test designed via a shape optimization approach was also designed and tested experimentally by Aquino et al. [3] to calibrate a yield function via FEMU. The material investigated was a DC04 mild steel with a thickness of 0.70 mm. Notched specimens are often used due to their easy machinability and rather heterogeneous strain field. Rossi et al. [37] tested notched specimens of stainless steel of 0.75 mm thickness at different material orientations to inversely identify a complex yield criterion. Also, Guner et al. [38] studied several variations of radius and widths for notched specimens, and the selected geometry was machined in the aluminum alloy AA6016-T4 with 1.0 mm of thickness and tested in several orientations to calibrate the Yld2000-2D yield criterion. Several works focused on using a cruciform specimen under biaxial loading to identify anisotropic yield function parameters. Cooreman et al. [39] performed a biaxial tensile test on a perforated cruciform specimen of a DC06 steel of 0.8 mm thickness to determine the hardening behavior and the yield locus. Teaca et al. [15] used standard mechanical tests to identify most of the material parameters and then non-conventional biaxial specimens to extract the information related to the yield surface shape in the biaxial tension range for an ES steel and a 1050 A aluminum, both of 1 mm thickness. Moreover, Zhang et al. [40] combined two non-conventional experiments: a geometry obtained via a shape optimization procedure and a perforated cruciform specimen, the same used in [21], that can generate the required equibiaxial tension. The two experiments were conducted on a universal tensile machine, one under uniaxial tensile loading and the other using a biaxial apparatus. A different approach to obtaining the biaxial stress state without the need for additional testing equipment was addressed by Macek et al. [10], who designed a heterogeneous mechanical test with a pronounced biaxial stress state close to the center of the specimen. Using a 304 stainless steel of 0.68 mm thickness, the data provided by the heterogeneous test was complemented with data provided by standard tensile tests performed in different directions to calibrate plastic anisotropy. With the same goal, Thoby [41], tested experimentally four specimen designs at 45° to the rolling direction to characterize the plastic anisotropic behavior of the AA2198-T351 alloy with 4 mm thickness.

Some of the aforementioned works have shown promising results in terms of test richness. However, there is still a need for further exploration and application of these advanced techniques in real experimental settings. Issues regarding specimen alignment and hence uniformity of the load application may arise particularly when dealing with non-symmetric samples. Also, from DIC, the sources of measurement error are numerous and related to the measurement environment: lighting, the CCD sensor noise, and lens quality, and the configuration of the workplace [25]. Also, errors from the speckle pattern and spatial resolution limitations can add complexity to the measurement of the displacement and strain fields. There is likely an impact on

the repeatability of the strain measurement due to the varying quality of the applied speckle pattern, which may propagate into variations in the inversely identified parameters. Strain information may be lost during the optical measurement mainly near the free edges of the geometries. Due to the lack of material points in those areas, data extraction can be challenging. Several issues may appear and impact the results, resulting in non-comparable numerical and experimental data. The introduction of noise in numerical data through the use of synthetic images is already working towards that goal [42]. However, analyzing experimentally the mechanical tests is crucial to verify the potential given to them by numerical models and to analyze their stability with regard to the materials as previous studies were only conducted for one material and Martins et al. [26] has shown the dependency of the strain field on the material used.

In a previous study, the potential of heterogeneous mechanical tests was numerically investigated and compared [20]. Five advanced heterogeneous mechanical tests were analyzed numerically and the mechanical information was used to compute key performance indicators. At the end of the work, a final ranking of the mechanical tests was proposed based on the richness and quality of the information they can provide. To validate the results, three of the five mechanical tests are chosen to be experimentally investigated. The first one, entitled Notched, was studied numerically and experimentally by Rossi et al. [12] and, consequently, used to identify the constitutive parameters of anisotropic plasticity models. With good machinability, this design presents a single geometric singularity that produces a heterogeneous strain field and a large plastic strain area. In turn, the D specimen, designed by [22], was obtained via an iterative process. The initial shape was designed by engineering intuition and then iteratively updated to present the widest range of strain states with a single test. Lastly, the TopOpt specimen, whose design methodology was first proposed in elasticity [28] and then improved for elastoplasticity [43]. Buckling is evidenced experimentally and predicted numerically for the TopOpt geometry [20]. Characterized by an out-of-plane displacement, this behavior is usually avoided in sheet metal forming works and is associated with compressive states. However, it was proposed to take advantage of the unusual behavior by using multi-DIC systems to increase the strain richness provided by the test. The Notched and Dshape were also analyzed along with a specimen geometry designed by topology optimization in elasticity [19]. Despite the similarity of the design technique between this design and the TopOpt, the TopOpt was designed assuming the elastoplastic behavior of the material. Results showed that the specimen designed with topology optimization presented the most heterogeneous strain field, however, it was chosen as the least robust when it comes to experimental bias due to its complex design and consequent mechanical fields. Therefore, the performance of a specimen with such a complex mechanical behavior needs to be investigated.

This work focuses on the experimental analysis of three heterogeneous mechanical tests, previously investigated numerically in [20], which are now subjected to an experimental procedure. Uniaxial tensile loading tests are performed with the three specimen designs and Stereo Digital Image Correlation is employed to extract the mechanical fields from the tests' surface. Due to their complex design, their repeatability is checked. As a follow-up of the previous work [20], the main goal is to confirm the

richness of the mechanical deformation when using real data as well as its sensitivity to different high-strength steels.

This paper is organized as follows: the next section, titled Experimental Setup, provides a detailed description of the selected specimen geometries, materials, and configuration of the test and DIC setups. The results are then presented and discussed in Section 3, where an analysis of the repeatability of the tests' behavior is made in the first place. Then, the performance of each test is investigated, taking into account the strain field richness through a mechanical indicator. The sensitivity of the TopOpt test to different high-strength steels is addressed. Finally, the paper culminates with the conclusions, where the main findings and limitations of the work are analyzed in the context of sheet metal characterization.

2 Experimental setup and testing procedure

2.1 Specimen geometries

In this work, three advanced mechanical tests are investigated: Notched, D, and TopOpt specimens, whose geometries and overall dimensions are shown in Figure 1. More details can be found in the original papers. In order to consider the repeatability of the tests, the dimensions of each geometry were measured, and the average and standard deviation values of the thickness and width of the specimens are presented in Table 1.

For each one of the specimen geometries, a rectangular section is added on each side for placing the grips of the testing machine: 40, 50, and 55 mm of length for the Notched, Dshape and TopOpt specimens, respectively. These complex shapes are cut by water jet. The uniaxial external load is applied in the Y direction of the specimen frame, which is at 45° to the rolling direction.

Table 1: Thickness and width measurements for five experimental runs of the three specimens (Notched, Dshape and TopOpt), including corresponding average and standard deviation values.

	Notched		Dshape		TopOpt	
	t [mm]	w [mm]	t [mm]	w [mm]	t [mm]	w [mm]
Ref.	0.800	40.00	0.800	50.00	0.800	93.00
Run 1	0.776	37.96	0.813	47.25	0.778	88.15
Run 2	0.772	37.63	0.813	47.23	0.822	87.79
Run 3	0.778	37.71	0.792	47.32	0.772	87.94
Run 4	0.788	37.85	0.799	47.12	0.812	88.07
Run 5	0.785	37.85	0.807	47.20	0.818	88.09
Average	0.780	37.80	0.805	47.22	0.801	88.01
Std.	0.006	0.130	0.009	0.073	0.024	0.144

2.2 Materials

Three different high-strength steels are investigated in this study: a dual-phase steels DP600 and DP780, and HF1050, provided in sheets of thickness 0.8, 1.5, and 1.0 mm,

Fig. 1: Geometries and dimensions of the heterogeneous mechanical tests: (a) Notched [12], (b) D [22], and (c) TopOpt[28]. The test frame is defined for each test geometry. The \vec{Y} is the tensile direction and it is oriented at 45° to the rolling direction.

respectively. The mechanical properties of the three materials were measured with tensile tests at several orientations to the rolling direction and are given in Table 2. The three steels exhibit values of the standard deviation of the plastic anisotropy coefficients, \bar{r} , closer to the isotropic value. Also, the Δr property, computed as an average of the plastic anisotropy coefficients, shows a weak in-plane anisotropy associated with the three materials. The HF1050 steel is the one with the highest ultimate yield stress, R_m .

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the DP600, DP780 and HF1050 high-strength steels.

	R_m [MPa]	\bar{r}	Δr	t [mm]
DP600	661.9	0.999	0.085	0.8
DP780	786.4	0.906	0.048	1.5
HF1050	1093.0	0.912	0.069	1.0

2.3 Test conditions

The experiments are conducted on an Instron 5969 testing machine, equipped with a load cell of 50 kN maximum capacity. The specimens are clamped on both sides and to ensure quasi-static conditions, a test speed of 1 mm/min for the Notched and 3 mm/min for the D and TopOpt specimens are used. Moreover, these values are set to

have a similar average strain state, though it may be less meaningful for heterogeneous tests. For the sake of example, for the DP600 steel, the tensile force recorded for the Notched specimen to achieve rupture was 10.6 kN while for the D specimen, it was 9.56 kN. The TopOpt test, due to its dimension compared to the others, requires a tensile force of 18.95 kN.

A stereo Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system is used to measure the deformation on the specimen surface during the test. Stereo DIC allows the recording of out-of-plane movements, which can be caused by misalignments of the camera to the specimen surface or by instabilities such as buckling [37]. This is done by pointing two cameras at the surface of the specimens. A reference image is taken when the specimen is at rest. Then, sets of images are recorded by both cameras simultaneously at a constant image capture rate of 1 Hz. By comparing two recorded pictures of the specimen captured by both cameras, it is possible to obtain the displacement and strain fields. The optical measurement requires the application of a random speckle pattern on the specimen surface that follows the deformation of the test. In this work, a spray-painting technique is used consisting of a matte white coat uniformly distributed and a layer of random black dots. An example of the speckle pattern before the test is illustrated in Figure 2 for each one of the specimen designs. A numerically generated speckle pattern, printed on the specimen surface using a UV printer, was also tested during this experimental campaign. However, in several trials, the paint cracked before the specimen did, making the correlation impossible and not allowing the result extraction. Therefore, the analysis presented in the following section includes only the specimens tested with the spray-applied speckle pattern.

Fig. 2: Speckle pattern applied by spray on the three specimens: (a) Notched, (b) D and (c) TopOpt.

Experimental data was collected using commercial software, VIC-3D [44], along with two 5-megapixel Basler acA2440-35um cameras, each having a maximum resolution of 2048 x 2448 pixels. The cameras were set up as presented in Table 3 and were synchronized with the load cell to capture the corresponding tensile force for each image. To maximize the accuracy of the results and take advantage of the camera sensor’s potential, the two cameras were placed vertically for the D and TopOpt specimens, as shown in Figure 3. For the TopOpt specimen, two stereo DIC setups were utilized, one on each side of the specimen.

Fig. 3: Experimental setup: (a) An apparatus with one DIC system was similarly mounted for the Notched and D specimens. For the Notched test, the cameras are placed side by side in the horizontal direction. (b) Two identical DIC systems are used for the TopOpt, one on each side of the test. A wood panel is added in the background to prevent saturation of both systems for TopOpt. Only a rectangular opening is cut for recording the images with system 2.

The post-processing analysis was performed using MatchID software [42]. For accurate results, it is crucial to carefully choose the correlation algorithm, subset size, and step size when obtaining the experimental displacement fields. In order to select the best DIC settings, a performance analysis is conducted. The goal of this analysis is to find a balance between strain resolution (i.e., the noise floor) and signal reconstruction (e.g., the von Mises strain) [40]. To achieve this, different combinations of DIC settings such as subset size, subset shape functions, interpolation functions, step size, and strain window size are used to compute strain fields. The optimal DIC settings are determined by considering the trade-off between noise and signal reconstruction. Based on this selection criterion, the optimal DIC settings for each specimen design are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Hardware configuration and settings for DIC analysis.

	Notched	D	TopOpt
Camera 0 (noise)	Basler ac A2440-35um 5MP (0.68%, 1.07%, 1.03%)		
Image resolution	2448 x 2048	2048 x 2448	2048 x 2448
Camera 1 (noise)	Basler ac A2440-35um 5MP (0.74%, 0.77%, 0.68%)		
Image resolution	2448 x 2048	2048 x 2448	2048 x 2448
Focal length [mm]	35		
Stereo angle [°]	25		
FOV [mm]	50x80	70x90	100x190
Distance [mm]	450	446	860
Correlation algorithm	ZNSSD		
Interpolation	Local bicubic splines		
Subset shape function	Quadratic		
Subset and step size	19/6	15/6	19/8
Image prefiltering	Gaussian		
Strain window and convention	7/Euler-Almansi		
Progress history	Spatial	Spatial	Spatial+Update reference
Noise floor (displacement)	3.9e-4	3.8e-3	1.4e-3

2.4 Mechanical richness indicator

In a previous work [20], key performance indicators were proposed to evaluate the potential of heterogeneous mechanical tests. Due to the numerical concept of the work, some metrics were computed based on the stress field. Since stress is not a quantity that can be experimentally measured, only the strain field richness indicator is here computed as in [45]. It can be defined as follows:

$$I_t = w_{r1} \frac{\text{Std}(\varepsilon_2/\varepsilon_1)}{w_{a1}} + w_{r2} \frac{(\varepsilon_2/\varepsilon_1)_R}{w_{a2}} + w_{r3} \frac{\text{Std}(\bar{\varepsilon}^{\text{eq}})}{w_{a3}} + w_{r4} \frac{\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{max}}^{\text{eq}}}{w_{a4}} + w_{r5} \frac{\text{Av}(\bar{\varepsilon}^{\text{eq}})}{w_{a5}}, \quad (1)$$

where ε_1 and ε_2 are, respectively, the major and minor principal strains in the sheet plane. The ratio between the minor and the major principal strains ($\varepsilon_2/\varepsilon_1$) is used to define the strain state space. In the original formulation of the indicator, the equivalent plastic strain, $\bar{\varepsilon}^{\text{P}}$, is used as an evaluation criterion. However, due to the experimental character of this work, the equivalent strain, $\bar{\varepsilon}^{\text{eq}}$, and its maximum value, $\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{max}}^{\text{eq}}$, are used instead. This indicator evaluates different features, from left to right in Equation (1): (i) the strain state standard deviation, (ii) the strain state range, (iii) the standard deviation, (iv) maximum and (v) average values of the equivalent strain. These terms can be divided into two main groups: strain state range and heterogeneity and strain level. The importance of each term is adjusted and normalized using absolute (w_{ai} , with $i \in [1, 5]$) and relative weights (w_{ri} , with $i \in [1, 5]$). The values chosen for these parameters, based on the original study performed with a mild steel [45], are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Absolute values and relative weights for the adjustment and normalization of the terms of I_t indicator [45].

w_{a1}	w_{a2}	w_{a3}	w_{a4}	w_{a5}	w_{r1}	w_{r2}	w_{r3}	w_{r4}	w_{r5}
1	4	0.25	1	1	0.3	0.03	0.17	0.4	0.1

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Test repeatability

Analyzing the repeatability of advanced mechanical tests is crucial due to the complexity of their geometry and the sensitivity of the techniques used. These tests provide detailed insights into critical material properties and behavior and, therefore, a thorough investigation of their repeatability is required. While homogeneous tests benefit from consistent conditions and test parameters, which lead to high repeatability by averaging strain over large areas and discarding the influence of material heterogeneity, heterogeneous tests do not offer this advantage. These inherently involve varied strain distributions and stress states across the specimen. These combined with the localized measurements make the results more susceptible to variations due to material heterogeneity. Due to that, for instance, a study by Fu et al. [46] adopts a double-notched specimen to run a VFM-based identification and analyzes the repeatability of the load-displacement curves and the temperature distributions of three experimental runs before the identification procedure. There are not many works discussing the need to analyze the repeatability of heterogeneous tests, but this sensitivity to local variations in material properties highlights the need for multiple experimental runs to evaluate the consistency and reliability of the test results.

In this work, two experimental runs are performed in the same conditions with each specimen design. First of all, the geometries' misalignment during the test is analyzed, which is likely to appear in this kind of experiment. Due to this, a non-uniform strain distribution may appear in the specimen. For each experiment, the displacement evolution was recorded during the test and this information allowed the creation of virtual extensometers that follow specific points at the specimen surface throughout the test. Figure 4 sets an example for one test of each specimen design, where the evolution of the deformation of three virtual extensometers along the \bar{Y} direction is represented. The three extensometers, each one with one color, were placed at the same height along the width of the specimens and the deformation evolution curve is represented with the same color. An average of the three evolution curves is represented by the black dashed line.

For the Notched specimen, the displacement evolution of the three extensometers is rather similar. The three curves would ideally overlap, however, due to the misalignment of the specimen, the displacement evolution is not symmetric. This can also be noted in Figure 5(a), in which the grips' parts of the specimens after the test are represented, the grips didn't pull the Notched specimen in an equal way and, therefore, there are more evident marks on the right side of the specimen. As a result, the displacement at rupture strongly depends on the location of the extensometer and

Fig. 4: Displacement evolution of the three virtual extensometers, with the same length, defined at different positions for the (a) Notched, (b) D and (c) TopOpt specimens. Each line represents the displacement of a pair of points with the respective color. The black dashed line represents the average evolution of the three extensometers.

the rupture will occur on one side of the specimen [47]. Regarding the D specimen, since the geometry is not vertically symmetric, the behavior of the left pair of points (orange) is different from the right one (green). This can be confirmed by the grips' marks of the D specimen depicted in Figure 5(b). Also, sliding also occurs at the beginning but at a different level for the three extensometers. Due to the symmetric design of the TopOpt specimen, both virtual extensometers on the sides of the specimen have similar behavior in contrast to the one at the center of the specimen. Based on Figure 5(c), it is worth noting that the TopOpt specimen is the one that presents more symmetric grips' marks.

Fig. 5: Details of the grips' marks after the mechanical test with the (a) Notched, (b) D and (c) TopOpt specimens. The width of the grips is 40, 50 and 40 mm, for the Notched, Dshape and TopOpt, respectively.

The information extracted from the virtual extensometers' deformation makes it possible to plot the load-local displacement curves related to each specimen design in Figure 6. For each specimen type, two test runs are analyzed and, from each one, the average displacement of the virtual extensometers is used to plot the load evolution. In the y-axis, the load value is divided by the initial thickness of the sheet specimen so that the load evolution curve does not account for dispersions in the specimens' dimensions. It is worth noting that the similarity of the load-local displacement curves is a key indicator of the test's ability to maintain stability and produce robust results across different experimental runs. Comparing the two tests with the Notched specimen, it can be noted the similar behavior between the two curves with a slight difference in the yielding part. Regarding the D specimen, the load level in the D07 test is higher than in the D05 and reaches rupture with a lower displacement. In contrast, despite the unusual out-of-plane behavior, the load-local displacement curves of the two runs of the TopOpt specimen are quite similar.

Fig. 6: Load-local displacement curves for two test runs with each specimen design: (a) Notched, (b) D and (c) TopOpt specimens. The load is divided by the initial thickness of the specimen to account for inaccuracies in the specimens' dimensions.

As stated in a previous work [20], the TopOpt specimen suffers from a buckling instability during a uniaxial tensile loading test, leading to an out-of-plane behavior of the specimen geometry. This event is represented, for the sake of example, for an experimental run, in Figure 7(c). The out-of-plane displacement is depicted in the transverse direction at several time steps through the test time until rupture. The grey curve corresponds to the beginning of the tensile test and the black one stands for the end of the test, where the displacement of the grips is 18.43 mm. In order to understand if this unstable behavior due to a buckling phenomenon can be repeatable, the out-of-plane displacement maps at the end of the test for the two experimental runs with the TopOpt specimen are represented in Figures 7(a) and (b). Overall, both specimens present identical configurations at the end of the test, being the minor differences between the displacement maps in the minimum and maximum values.

The three tests were analyzed across different experimental runs and it is possible to conclude that their behavior is quite similar. There is a dependency of the results on the speckle pattern technique and therefore some differences arise in the Notched

Fig. 7: Analysis of the TopOpt specimen out-of-plane behavior: displacement maps at the end of test for the (a) TopOpt03 and (b) TopOpt04 experimental runs; (c) Evolution of the out-of-plane displacement across the transversal direction through the test time, from the grey (no grips' displacement) to the black line (end of the test).

and D tests due to that. Despite the out-of-plane behavior, the TopOpt test presented robust results in the two test runs, meaning a repeatable load behavior and strain evolution. For each specimen type, an experimental run is chosen as a representative one from the two presented previously. For the Notched and D specimens, the test performed with the spray technique is chosen, Notched05 and D05, respectively. For the TopOpt, although both are painted with spray, the TopOpt04 is chosen to be further analyzed.

3.2 Mechanical richness analysis

This section provides a comprehensive comparison of the three mechanical tests, Notched, D, and TopOpt taking into account their performance and potential to provide important mechanical information. In the first place, Figure 8 depicts the principal strain distributions captured at the last frame before fracture as well as the principal strain diagrams associated with each specimen. Regarding the strain maps, the maximum and minimum strain distributions are represented for the Notched, D, and TopOpt specimens. For the TopOpt, the strain distributions of both surfaces,

extracted by DIC systems 1 and 2, are shown. The information from both systems is also presented in the principal strain diagrams in different colors.

Fig. 8: Experimental maximum and minimum principal strain fields of the (a) Notched, (b) D, and (c) TopOpt (DIC systems 1 and 2) specimens. Principal strain diagrams for the DP600 with the information exhibited by: (a) Notched, (b) D, and (c) TopOpt specimens.

For the Notched specimen, the highest major strain values are localized in the center part of the specimen and the rest is under low strain values. In contrast, the D specimen presents a more dispersed strain field, presenting some areas where the

higher values are localized. These are placed near the edges and therefore may be missed during the DIC measurement. Also, due to the small thickness of the thin arm, the extraction of information may not be possible. The peak value is achieved in the thin arm as well as rupture, as represented in Figure 9(b). For the TopOpt specimen, the strain fields from both surfaces are presented. Due to the out-of-plane behavior, the mechanical behavior of one surface is different from the other, one is subjected to tension, and the other to compression. In addition, the peak values are localized in the center part, where the fracture occurs, and also in the upper and bottom center parts, where the specimen bends. It is worth noting that the Notched specimen due to its similarity to the well-known dogbone specimen presents predominantly material points in uniaxial tension. In turn, the D specimen presents points in pure shear besides the points in uniaxial tension filling almost the entire strain state range for small and intermediate magnitude values. The TopOpt specimen stands out with a significantly higher heterogeneity of strain states, presenting material points between plane strain compression and equibiaxial tension with a greater emphasis on uniaxial tension and plane strain compression.

Fig. 9: Specimens after fracture: (a) Notched, (b) D and (c) TopOpt.

The mechanical richness indicator (cf. subsection 2.4) has been computed for each test design. In Figure 10, the values of the mechanical indicator for each test configuration are presented as well as each term of I_t (cf. Equation (1)). The experimental data used for the computation of this indicator is associated with the last frame before the specimen's rupture. Based on the overall indicator value, the ranking is similar to the one obtained with virtual results in a previous work [20]. The TopOpt presents the highest indicator value followed by the D and the Notched specimens. Regarding the strain state standard deviation, Figure 11 depicts the data points distribution of the three tests over the strain state range that is chosen to be limited between -1 and 15. The information was extracted from the DIC points after the post-processing. The TopOpt specimen presents a higher value of the standard deviation since the material points are more evenly distributed across the strain state range presented with

Fig. 10: Values of the mechanical indicator I_t , proposed by Souto et. al. [45], and its terms computed individually for all the test designs.

a higher concentration between uniaxial and plane strain tension. It can be noticed a scarce distribution between uniaxial and plane strain compression for the Notched and D specimens in comparison to the TopOpt. Limits are imposed to the strain state range, explaining the same value for the D and TopOpt specimens for this term. Concerning the standard deviation and the average values of the equivalent strain, the D specimen exceeds the TopOpt one. As shown in Figure 8, the D specimen presents a more distributed strain field magnitude, leading to a higher average value. The equivalent strain peak values are higher in the TopOpt specimen but are extremely localized. This makes them difficult to be processed and extracted by DIC. With the aid of the principal strain diagrams, it is worth noting that the D specimen has a more important distribution in the tension strain states, explaining its higher term value. For the shear term, although the TopOpt also presents material points in this range, the magnitude value of the D specimen points is higher. The advantage of the TopOpt specimen is the ability to have material points both in tension and compression with interesting strain magnitude values in a single experiment. This happens due to its out-of-plane behavior during the test. Also, it presents material points in biaxial and plane strain tension and compression. A similar analysis was made in a previous work [20], where this mechanical indicator was computed for analyzing the data richness provided by these tests numerically. When compared to this work, the Notched and D specimens provide a similar quantity of information on the same strain states, mostly around uniaxial tension. Regarding the TopOpt specimen, the data on uniaxial tension is identically placed. The information extracted experimentally from

Fig. 11: Data points distribution over the strain state range of the (a) Notched, (b) D and (c) TopOpt specimens.

the surface under compression is placed mostly around plane strain compression while the numerical data pointed to uniaxial compression.

3.3 Test sensitivity to different high-strength steels

In the previous sections, the TopOpt specimen is compared to another two heterogeneous mechanical tests for a DP600 steel. This section is focused on the TopOpt test and its potential is analyzed for three advanced high-strength steels: DP600, DP780 and HF1050. The mechanical information regarding these materials can be found in Table 2. The sensitivity of the results to the different materials is analyzed as well as the robustness of the potential of the test. Therefore, in a similar way to Figure 6, the load-local displacement curves are presented for two different experimental runs of each material in Figure 12. Since the thickness of the metal sheet is different for each material, the load is presented taking into account the initial section of the specimen. It can be noted that a larger load level is required to deform the HF1050 and the DP780 due to their ultimate yield stress and thickness, cf. Table 2. However, it is required a lower displacement of the grips to lead the specimen to rupture. For instance, the TopOpt specimens with DP600, DP780 and HF1050 reach rupture with displacements of 18.43, 10.60, and 9.78 mm, respectively. It is worth noting that the two experimental runs with the DP600 are the most similar, while for the other materials, rupture is achieved earlier for one of the runs.

Figure 13 shows the out-of-plane displacement map of the TopOpt specimen with the three materials, DP600, DP780, and HF1050, just before rupture. From both figures, it is worth noting that the TopOpt specimen with the DP600 presents the

Fig. 12: Load-local displacement curves of two different experimental runs with the TopOpt specimen for each material (DP600, DP780, and HF1050).

Fig. 13: Out-of-plane displacement map of the TopOpt specimens with (a)DP600, (b)DP780 and (c)HF1050 steels at the end of the test.

highest out-of-plane displacement value. This is due to (i) the lowest thickness of the metal sheet of the three materials and (ii) the lowest yield stress of the three.

Regarding the strain field information, Figure 14 depicts the principal strain diagrams associated with the TopOpt specimen for each material (DP600, DP780 and HF1050). In the diagram associated with the TopOpt test, it is shown the information from both surfaces extracted by systems 1 and 2. The strain field information presented in the diagrams is identical for the three materials despite the strain level. Additionally, for each test, there is a difference between the information extracted by both systems in the location where the specimen bends which has a different behavior in system 1 or 2, being under tension or compression, respectively. This is the main difference that can be noted in the principal strain diagrams between both systems

Fig. 14: Principal strain diagrams related to the TopOpt specimen for the three materials: (a) DP600, (b) DP780, and (c) HF1050. Data provided by both systems (1 and 2) is presented.

(grey and black colors). While System 2 shows material points under plane strain compression, system 1 presents in contrast points in plane strain tension. However, the majority of the points are common to both and are under uniaxial tension. Regarding the DP780 TopOpt test, there is a significant difference in the strain level between both surfaces. This can be noted in the principal strain diagram, where there are points extracted by system 2 under uniaxial tension with higher strain levels. This happened due to the impossibility of system 1 of extracting data from this time on due to the bad resolution of the images. Both the DP780 and HF1050 tests present more material points under plane strain tension than the DP600. In turn, the DP600 test has material points under equibiaxial tension. This may be due to the higher bending of this test when compared to the others that have a lower out-of-plane displacement (cf. Figure 13).

To quantify the information given by the principal strain diagrams and the strain field distributions, the strain richness indicator is computed similarly to the previous section. Figure 15 depicts the indicator value as well as its terms individually for the TopOpt with the three different materials. The final indicator value is quite similar between the three tests with the highest value associated with the DP780 test. Regarding the equivalent strain level, the DP600 TopOpt test presents the best performance, however, the gap to the others, mainly to the DP780 one, is small. The strain state standard deviation is higher in both the DP600 and DP780 tests due to the higher number of points under plane strain tension while the DP600 test presents more points concentrated in the uniaxial tension state. Due to this, since the gap to the other is higher, this test isn't the one with the highest indicator value.

Overall, it is shown that the performance of the TopOpt specimen is quite similar even when different high-strength steels are used. Even though the strain level achieved by the test when using the HF1050 steel is lower, the strain state heterogeneity remains identical for the three materials. Therefore, it is possible to prove the robustness of the test and its potential to be used in advanced material behavior characterization.

Fig. 15: Values of the mechanical indicator I_t , proposed by Souto et. al. [45], and its terms computed individually for the TopOpt specimen with the three materials.

4 Concluding remarks

This work aims to analyze the potential of three heterogeneous mechanical tests for characterizing sheet metal behavior when using data from real experiments. Heterogeneous tests are able to provide a substantial amount and diversity of mechanical information in a single experiment. However, issues related to the experimental task may arise and impact the results' quality, leading to non-comparable numerical and experimental data. Therefore, it is crucial to verify the potential given to them by numerical models.

First, the repeatability of the three tests is investigated across different experimental runs. The complexity associated with their geometry and the measurement technique may influence the mechanical behavior and, therefore, the mechanical information extracted. The results showed that, despite the complex designs, these tests have proven to be highly repeatable when performed in similar conditions.

The mechanical information richness is analyzed based on the strain level and strain state range and heterogeneity. Based on the principal strain diagrams and the quantification of their information by a mechanical indicator, the results showed that the TopOpt test provided a larger quantity and diversity of mechanical data. Due to its out-of-plane behavior during the test, information was extracted by both surfaces, leading to the simultaneous existence of tensile and compressive states in a single experiment. When compared to numerical data, the Notched and D specimens provide a similar quantity of information on the same strain states. Regarding the TopOpt

specimen, experimental information extracted from the surface under compression is placed mostly around plane strain compression while the numerical data pointed to uniaxial compression.

Finally, the sensitivity of the TopOpt test behavior to different high-strength steels was investigated, resulting in a similar amount of information provided by each test. Despite the different strain level achieved by each test, mainly due to the different mechanical properties, the same strain states were identified. It is possible to confirm the test's ability to yield similar mechanical behavior data across three different high-strength steels highlighting its robustness and reliability

Through the experimental analysis of these heterogeneous mechanical tests, it is possible to prove that their potential remains unchanged when real experimental data is used. By demonstrating their effectiveness in providing relevant information for material behavior characterization, this work opens the way for the improvement of model calibration procedures.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the Research Fund for Coal and Steel under grant agreement No 888153. This paper was also supported by the projects UIDB/00481/2020 and UIDP/00481/2020 - Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, DOI 10.54499/UIDB/00481/2020 and DOI 10.54499/UIDP/00481/2020. M. Gonçalves is grateful to the FCT for the Ph.D. grant Ref. UI/BD/151257/2021 and to the ESAFORM association for the mobility grant. The authors would like to acknowledge Anthony Jegat from IRDL for his invaluable expertise and help with the experiments. Disclaimer

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